

Descriptive Metadata for P-Demotion Typological Database

This descriptive metadata has been designed for the interactive P-demotion typological database. The database is one of the milestones of the Polonez Bis Project, led by the Principal Investigator Katarzyna Janic, and conducted from October 1, 2022, to September 30, 2024 at Adam Mickiewicz University. Upon the project completion, the database has been made publicly accessible on the project website: <https://katjan21.web.amu.edu.pl/>. The database remains open to further refinement and expansion. Any inconsistencies should be reported to Katarzyna Janic at Katarzyna.Janic@amu.edu.pl.

The interactive, crosslinguistic database systematically documents the phenomenon of P-demotion across 55 genealogically diverse languages. P-demotion is observed in verb valency-changing alternations where the P argument (object) of a transitive construction loses its status as a core argument. This change in verbal valency may be encoded by a voice marker. The loss of the core status by the P argument manifests differently across languages. For instance, it may involve changes in P-encoding properties, such as indexing and flagging, or the elimination of this argument from the valency slot, which may also alter its indexing on the verb. The phenomenon of P-demotion thus arises from the operation on verbal valency and results in a syntactically intransitive construction, where the demoted P-argument can be expressed as an oblique, incorporated, or fully eliminated. Given, that these constructions share two main features: (i) demotion of the P-argument and (ii) retention of the argument structure, where agents remain agents and patients remain patients, they are expected to exhibit formal and/or functional overlap. The morphosyntactic strategy a language employs to demote P argument depends on language-specific properties and functions associated with these strategies.

Based on the multivariate typology by Bickel (2010, 2011, 2015), which posits that every linguistic phenomenon can be decomposed into crosslinguistically comparable variables, the phenomenon of P demotion was systematically analyzed by breaking it down into formal and functional variables. Formal variables encompassed encoding properties of the core arguments A, P, and S in P-demotion alternations, such as flagging (e.g., case, adposition) and indexation (e.g., verb agreement, cross-referencing), along with the presence of voice marking and variation in P-oblique flagging. In contrast, functional variables were related to various types of P-demotion constructions alone and included properties of the P argument such as referentiality, affectedness, animacy, person, and number. The functional variable of referentiality refers to all types of P-demotion constructions, whereas affectedness, animacy, person, and number were applicable only to P-oblique constructions.

Data for the interactive database was collected by three project members: Principal Investigator Katarzyna Janic, Co-Investigator Krzysztof Stroński, and Ph.D. student Mohammad Tavakoli. The data collection took place from 2022 till 2024. To collect data, the project members mined reference and descriptive grammars, dissertations, and other grammatical sketches to collect the existing data, referred to as secondary data. They also consulted the HH archive, specifically the Gramfinder database, which hosts a rich collection of grammatical resources and typological studies. The research team additionally accessed existing datasets such as 'Typology of Antipassive Coding Patterns', previously developed by the Principal Investigator and colleagues and made available in Zenodo.

The data obtained through grammar mining were initially stored online as a dataset in Google Sheets. To build this dataset, the concept of P-demotion was decomposed into structural, i.e., formal and functional variables across 55 genealogically unrelated languages. Should the information be not available in the consulted document, an effort was made to contact the language expert for further clarification. The data were subsequently converted to an Excel document and made available through the Zenodo repository under 'P-demotion: Extended sample'. The examples collected through grammar mining were first stored in individual word files, each labelled with the language name and an index, and subsequently integrated into the interactive database.

the interactive database aimed for a balanced language sample, hence one language per family was selected, based on the genealogical classification in Glottolog. However, a few exceptions were made for larger families, such as Indo-European, Austronesian, Sino-Tibetan, and Pama-Nyungan, where we included data from two to four languages per family. Additionally, two languages were selected from

the smaller Eskimo-Aleut family, as P-oblique alternations play there a role in alignment shifts. In all these cases, it was ensured that languages represented distinct sub-branches.

Project members regularly cross-checked coding decisions to maintain consistency and accuracy. An additional strength of the database is its extensive range of structural variables (see below for formal and functional variables), each accompanied by specific values and comments from different sources. These comments, cited directly from original sources, offer insights into the rationale for particular coding decisions, enabling readers to consult the cited sources for further context on each variable.

The interactive database results from the dataset 'P-demotion: Extended sample' uploaded on Zenodo. This dataset that was converted into the interactive database application, enriched by the collected examples. The development of the interactive database was a collaborative effort led by Maciej Danielak and Paweł Przybysz, who worked closely with Katarzyna Janic as co-investigators of the project. Their tasks were to (i) design and build the database architecture, (ii) process and integrate data into the system, (iii) select and implement appropriate technologies, and (iv) conduct testing to identify and resolve potential errors prior to public release. The Principal Investigator also established a data verification procedure, under which a project member Wojciech Zeyland reviewed and refined data entries to ensure accuracy and address any inconsistencies.

The interactive database serves a dual purpose. First, it provides a comprehensive platform for exploring the grammatical properties (i.e., structural variables) of P-demotion constructions, thereby yielding valuable insights for comparative and crosslinguistic research. Second, it follows contemporary linguistic standards, including reproducibility, data sharing, and reusability. The access to the database application requires a computer with internet and a web browser.

Data description

1. LgNameGlott: the name of the language used by language experts
2. LgTop-level family: the family name of a given language, based on <https://glottolog.org/>
3. LgMacroarea: the macroareas name of a given language, based on <https://glottolog.org/>

The following questions define the data collected in dataset 'P-demotion: Extended sample'. Specifically, they pertain to structural variables (categorical data) associated with the P-demotion phenomenon and were answered with one of the following options: YES, NO, N/I (no information), or N/A (non-applicable). Independent variables address distinct aspects of P-demotion, such as *Is there P-demotion through incorporation?* Independent variables refer to a specific aspect of P demotion and are followed by dependent variables. These, in turn, are contingent on the independent variable, for instance, *Is there morphological incorporation of P?* This means that if a language does not exhibit P-demotion through incorporation, the answer to this independent variable should be NO, and all associated dependent variables (e.g., *Is there morphological incorporation of P?*) should be marked as N/A. Conversely, if an independent variable is attested in a language, it should be marked YES, and the dependent variables that follow must be answered with either YES or NO, based on the observed data. Finally, if the relevant information is not available in the consulted sources, the variable were marked as N/I. N/I is applicable only to dependent variables. Certain variables below are accompanied by explanations to involve specific knowledge or additional clarification when required.

P-realization

1. Is there P demotion through incorporation? (Independent variables)

We search to determine the following: Does noun incorporation affect the valency of the derived verb? Do incorporated nouns have the effect of detransitivizing a transitive verb?

2. Is there a morphological incorporation of P?
3. Is the morphological incorporation of P restricted to a few generic nouns?
4. Is the morphological incorporation of P restricted to a few verbs?

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5. Is there a pseudo-incorporation of P?
6. Is pseudo-incorporation of P restricted?
7. Is there P demotion through P-oblique expression? (**Independent variables**)

By oblique we refer to any noun phrase or adpositional phrase that is a constituent of a clause (and not of another noun phrase) and that is not an argument, i.e. that is not governed by the predicate (Comrie et al. 2021: 519).

8. Is it possible to omit a P oblique?

In some antipassive constructions, the referent of the initial P may be optionally expressed as an oblique NP or as an incorporated noun ('patientful antipassives'), but in some others, it is obligatorily left unexpressed ('patientless antipassives'); (Creissels 2023: 389).

9. Is there P demotion through P elimination? (**Independent variables**)

Unexpressed P must have unspecified reading based on Creissels (2023: 518): In a general account of valency alternations, it is important to distinguish between unexpressed nuclear participants interpreted anaphorically, and unexpressed nuclear participants interpreted as unspecified. The position explicitly adopted in this book is that anaphoric zeros are part of the pronominalization system, and consequently must be excluded from the notion of valency alternation, whereas the possibility of expressing unspecified nuclear participants by simply omitting the corresponding NP, as in English: The child ate (the cake), is a particular type of valency alternation. The uncoded valency alternations involving a change in transitivity are grouped under the term AMBITRANSITIVITY, with two main subtypes: A-ambitransitivity (in which the S of the intransitive construction corresponds to the A of the transitive construction) and P-ambitransitivity (in which the S of the intransitive construction corresponds to the P of the transitive construction) (Creissels 2021: 34).

Voice

10. Is there proper voice marking to demote P? (**Independent variables**)

VOICE is used as a general term for morphological operations on verbs regulating the relationship between the syntactic roles of noun phrases and how their referents participate in the event denoted by the verb (Creissels 2021: 267). VOICE is a general term for morphological operations on verbs regulating the relationship between the syntactic role of noun phrases and how their referents participate in the event denoted by the verb (Creissels 2021: 9). By morphological operation, we mean - reduplication, - affixation, - cliticization.

11. Is there synthetic (affix, clitic) marking to demote P?
12. Is there synthetic (reduplication) marking to demote P?

We search to determine: Does reduplication have syntactic detransitivising effects in a language? Does reduplication have a syntactic impact on the transitivity of the verb?

13. Is there analytical marking to demote P?

The morphological coding of voice alternations may take the form of a morphological operation affecting directly the verbal stem (affixation or other) or involve the formation of analytical verb forms (complex predicates) (Creissels 2021: 271). For example, in many European languages, passivization involves analytical verb forms in which the verb involved in

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the voice alternation takes the form of a non-finite form commonly designated as past participle or passive participle, whereas tense and agreement morphology attaches to a verb 'be' in auxiliary function, as in English: The letter will be written by me (Creissels 2021: 271).

14. Is there voice look-alike marking to demote P? **(Independent variables)**

This point refers to a category not described by the author as a valency-changing operator but which behaves, at least to some extent, like a valency-changing operator (=voice marker).

Relation between verbs

15. Is there a formally privative opposition between the verbs in P demotion alternation? **(Independent variables)**

Privative opposition implies morphologically oriented voice alternations. (P demotion) can, in principle, be distinguished from a base voice via a formally privative opposition between a zero-marked active and a nonzero-marked antipassive (Zuniga & Kittila 2019: 113).

16. Is there a formally equipollent opposition between the verbs in P demotion alternation? **(Independent variables)**

Voice alternations may also involve verb forms showing the same degree of morphological complexity in both alternating constructions, with the consequence that there is no obvious reason for treating one of them as derived from the other. Such situations can be characterized as involving EQUIPOLLENT VOICE MARKING (Creissels 2021: 269). The two verb forms involved in a voice alternation show an equal degree of morphological complexity (Creissels 2021: 300). A formally equipollent opposition between the base and (P demotion) forms can be the use of morphemes marking either voice (Zuniga & Kittila 2019: 113).

17. Is the formal relationship between the verbs in the P demotion alternation analyzed as suppletivism? **(Independent variables)**

Suppletivism refers to the strategy in which transitive and intransitive verbs of P demotion are completely different or differ in such a way that their formal relationship cannot be analyzed as a particular instance of some more or less regular pattern. The possible formal relationship between the verbs in P demotion alternation: SUPPLETIVISM. SUPPLETIVISM STRATEGY: in a suppletive verbal pair, the verbs are completely different or differ in such a way that their formal relationship cannot be analyzed as a particular instance of some more or less regular pattern (Creissels 2021: 566). SUPPLETIVISM strategy: in a suppletive pair of verbs, the formal difference between the verbs cannot be analyzed as a particular instance of some more or less regular pattern (Creissels 2021: 562).

One Voice marker

18. Is there one voice marker (affix, clitic) to demote P?
 19. Is there a voice marker (affix, clitic) in the P-incorporation clause?
 20. Is there a P-incorporation clause without a voice marker (affix, clitic)?
 21. Is there a voice marker (affix, clitic) in the P-oblique clause?
 22. Is there a P-oblique clause without a voice marker (affix, clitic)?
 23. Is there a voice marker (affix, clitic) in the P-unexpressed clause?
 24. Is there a P-unexpressed clause without a voice marker (affix, clitic)?

Many voice markers

25. Are there many voice markers (affixes, clitics) to demote P?

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26. Is there a voice marker (affix, clitic) in the P-incorporation clause?
27. Is there a P-incorporation clause without a voice marker (affix, clitic)?
28. Is there a voice marker (affix, clitic) in the P-oblique clause?
29. Is there a P-oblique clause without a voice marker (affix, clitic)?
30. Is there a voice marker (affix, clitic) in the P-unexpressed clause?
31. Is there a P-unexpressed clause without a voice marker (affix, clitic)?

Voice stacking

32. Can morphological voice markers (affixes, clitics) stack on the verb in the P-demotion clause?
(Independent variables)

Flagging

33. Is there flagging in the language? (Independent variables)

By flagging we mean a case (ergative case for A in a transitive main clause and / nominative case for A in a transitive main clause) or preposition. 'I designate as a zero case the case form of nouns that coincides with the form used in isolation for quotation and labeling' (Creissels 2021: 64).

34. Is an A argument flagged in an initial discursively neutral clause?
35. Is a P argument flagged in an initial discursively neutral clause?
36. Is a P argument always flagged in an initial discursively neutral clause?
37. Is there DOM?

Differential object marking (DOM): a) is the asymmetric variety of differential P flagging. Asymmetrical coding means unflagging P vs. flagging P (consult Creissels 2023: 154). b) Symmetric differential P flagging (consult Creissels 2023: 156).

38. Is an S argument flagged in a discursively neutral P-demotion clause?
39. Is a P argument obliquely flagged in a discursively neutral P-demotion clause?
40. Is there an unflagged P-oblique in a discursively neutral P-demotion clause?
41. Is there a variation in the P-oblique flagging?

Indexation

42. Is there indexation in the language? (Independent variables)
43. Is an A argument indexed on a verb in an initial discursively neutral clause?
44. Is an A argument always indexed on a verb in an initial discursively neutral clause?
45. Is a P argument indexed on a verb in an initial discursively neutral clause?
46. Is a P argument always indexed on a verb in an initial discursively neutral clause?
47. Is an S argument indexed on a verb in a discursively neutral P-demotion clause?
48. Is the presence of S indexation conditioned in a discursively neutral P-demotion clause?

Referentiality

49. Is there an incorporated P typically non-referential? (Independent variables)

usually, frequently, often, systematically, also COUNT as 'typically. *sometimes, *occasionally DOES NOT COUNT as 'typically' because they do not reveal any tendency.

50. Is there a non-referential incorporated P with a generic (i.e., non-specific) interpretation?

Generic expressions with non-specific reference (...). A referent can either be understood as an individual referent or as a generic expression referring not to any specific = referring to the kind (Bickel et al. 2007: 16). Referent can either be understood as individual or as kind denoted

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by the expression (generic). Noun incorporation plays an active role in discourse. Incorporated noun can be interpreted as a generic NPs with no particular referent (Baker et al. 2005: 145).

51. Is there a non-referential incorporated P with an indefinite (i.e., non-specific) interpretation?
 52. Can an incorporated P be referential (e.g., with the indefinite interpretation)? (Independent variables)

The Object is individuated, i.e., easily recognized as a uniquely identifiable element (Cooreman 1988: 573).

53. Is there a P-oblique typically non-referential? (Independent variables)

usually, frequently, often, systematically, also COUNT as 'typically. *sometimes, *occasionally DOES NOT COUNT as 'typically' because they do not reveal any tendency.

54. Is there a non-referential P oblique with a generic (i.e., non-specific) interpretation?
 55. Is there a non-referential P oblique with an indefinite (i.e., non-specific) interpretation?
 56. Can a P oblique be referential (e.g., with the (in)definite interpretation)? (Independent variables)
 57. Is there an unexpressed P typically non-referential? (Independent variables)

usually, frequently, often, systematically, also COUNT as 'typically. *sometimes, *occasionally DOES NOT COUNT as 'typically' because they do not reveal any tendency.

58. Is there a non-referential unexpressed P with a generic (i.e., non-specific) interpretation?
 59. Is there a non-referential unexpressed P with an indefinite (i.e., non-specific) interpretation?
 60. Can an unexpressed P with a voice marker be referential (e.g., with the (in)definite interpretation)? (Independent variables)

Affectedness

61. Does the property of affectedness condition the demotion of P to an oblique? (Independent variables)

Animacy

62. Does the property of animacy condition the demotion of P to an oblique? (Independent variables)
 63. Can the animate human P argument be demoted to an oblique?
 64. Can the animate non-human P argument be demoted to an oblique?
 65. Can the inanimate human P argument be demoted to an oblique?

Person

66. Does the property of person condition the demotion of P to an oblique? (Independent variables)
 67. Can the 1st or 2nd person P argument be demoted to an oblique?
 68. Can the 3rd person P argument be demoted to an oblique?

Number

69. Does the property of number condition the demotion of P to an oblique? (Independent variables)
 70. Can the singular P argument be demoted to an oblique?
 71. Can the plural P argument be demoted to an oblique?

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TAM properties

- 72. Does the P-demotion entail a shift in the TAM properties of a transitive verb? (**Independent variables**)
- 73. Is a shift in the TAM properties of a transitive verb regular?
- 74. Is a shift in the TAM properties of a transitive verb specific to a particular type of P-demotion clause?

Lexicon

- 75. Is P demotion lexically conditioned? (**Independent variables**)

Does P demotion apply to any verb or is conditioned by the lexical meaning of the verb? P demotion can be restricted to a specific group of verb, e.g. antagonistic verbs, psycho-verbs?

- 76. Is lexically conditioned P demotion productive?
- 77. Is lexically conditioned P demotion specific to a particular type of P-demotion clause?

Lexicalization

- 78. Does the P-demotion produce lexicalization effects? (**Independent variables**)
- 79. Are lexicalization effects specific to a particular type of P-demotion clause?
- 80. Are lexicalization effects regular in a P demotion clause?